
**Role of Indian Industrial Sector in Employment
(For the period of 2010-11 to 2019-20)**

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Abstract

India is number one populated country in the world and giving employment to them is the biggest challenge in front of governing bodies. The sector wise contribution in GDP for financial year 2021-22 agriculture sector has accounted 18.80%, industries 28.20% and service sector 53%. The agriculture and allied sectors are employing the major percentage of employment accounting 41.40% but it is contributing only 18.80%, industrial sector is accounting 27.60% and employing 17%. The service sector is contributing 53% in G.D.P. and accounting more than 30% of employment. The industrial sector is providing promising and steady employment to most populated country since its introduction. The different types of sectors of industries like agriculture and food processing, automobile, petro chemicals, chemicals, aviation, cement, steel are also some examples which are giving the employment opportunities. The government policies are favorable to industries which resulting attraction to FDI.

• Introduction

The economies of the nations are depending upon the various sectors like Primary, Secondary and Tertiary sectors. Now day new sector is developed and it is known as Research and Development. Whenever the economies are undeveloped at that they have to rely upon the primary sector. The journey of industrialization started in 1770 in Britain. Industrialization started with the development of steam, water and mechanical equipment in cotton industries. The first-generation industries were processing cotton all over the world. The cotton industries started in India in the year 1854 from Mumbai and the journey of industrialization begins. The journey of cotton mill and jute mills reached at 378 nos. till 1998. The industries of the India started with the help of foreign capital and management. The coal mining sector started its journey in the year 1772 from Raniganj. The sectors like cement, glass, soaps, sugar, paper, chemical industries have started slowly in India in that phase. The development of the industries before independence in India was very inadequate and insufficient. The world has seen second industrial revolution started

in the year 1870. The second industrial revolution was based on the electricity and mass production. The third industrial revolution started in the year 1950 which was based on the Electronics, IT and Automatic production technology. The third industrial revolution has developed world economy and made world 10 times wealthier. The third world industrial revolution required higher number of skilled workers. The third world revolution made high amount of production and revenues. The lakhs of new firms established in third world revolution. The third world revolution is also known as Digital Revolution. The current world is undergoing from the fourth industrial revolution which is depending upon Artificial Intelligence and advanced technologies. The system of industries is based on the CPS (Cyber Physical System).

• Objectives

1. To study the history of Industrialization.
2. To study the Industrialization in India.
3. To study the role of industries in an Indian economy.
4. To study the role industries in employment.

- **Research Methodology**

The research paper is based on the secondary data which is collected from the various websites, research reports of the various government agencies. The government of India is publishing the various reports on the industrial establishment and development of an economy. The analytical and statistical research methods are used for the data collection and analysis in this research.

- **Review of Literature**

1. Mrs. Manjula (2022) studied the creation of employment from industrial sector. Where she studied the limited capital resources industries have created good amount of employment by labour intensive industries. The industries have created 16% of employment in an economy. Researcher has mentioned that the increasing industries are lowering the unemployment and poverty rates.
2. Sudhakar, P., Padmavathi, A., & Kumar, N. B. K. (2012) have studied the employment trend in India. The researchers have found that the growth of the population is higher in India and the numbers of employment opportunities are limited. The study also mentioned that the Five Year plans played biggest role in creation of employment opportunities. The researchers have also shown that the employment is an important aspect of economic development.
3. Mogtadaee, A., Nezhad, M. Z. & Ansari, E (2006) studied the role of small industries in employment generation and economic development in Maharashtra & Khuzestan. The Researchers have used t test and chi square statistical tests. The study has analyzed the status of small scale industries in specific areas. The study has found the investments in large scale industries by Iran and Maharashtra, Khuzestan created job opportunities in small scale industries.

4. Dr. Pujar, Uma. (2014) studies the MSMEs role in employment. The researcher has found that the MSMEs industries has played vital role in socio economic development. The MSME sector is contributing 45% manufacturing output and 40% exports of the country. The MSMEs is providing 5, 95, 00, 000 numbers employment. The MSMEs businesses are creating self employment and wage employment in an economy of India.

- **Meaning Industries**

The industries are defined as the processing of inputs to get the output. The industries are creating finished goods from raw materials. The industries are involved in procurement, processing and creation of the finished goods. The industries are also classified under different categories or levels. The first category of industries is producing raw materials for other industries. These first levels of industries are extracting from the natural resources or minerals the industries are known as coal mining, forestry and fishing.

The second levels of industries are the industries which are converting raw materials into usable products by processing it. The example of such type of industries is making bakery products from the wheat flour. These industries are known as value addition making industries.

The Third levels of industries are the service industries are providing support to second level and primary industries. These are the essential services for the industries to grow and develop their market. The major service industries are financial institutes, education, transportation, education, hospitals and others.

- **World Scenario of Industries**

According to the report published by the IBIS world research firm the employment is as follows

Table No. 1.1 The worldwide Employment availability by industry

Sr. No.	Name of the Industry	Employment
1	Consumer Electronics Manufacturing	1,75,18,424
2	Commercial Real Estate	1,71,64,710
3	Fast food and Restaurants	1,34,58,146
4	HR and Recruitment Services	1,04,36,002
5	Apparel Manufacturing	96,75,672
6	Coal Mining	89,18,489
7	Travel & Tourism	86,84,644
8	Commercial Banks and Financial Institutes	80,76,796
9	Auto Parts & Accessories Manufacturing	80,60,047
10	Hotels & Resorts	79,03,412

(Source:- <https://www.ibisworld.com/global/market-research-reports/global-consumer-electronics-manufacturing-industry/>)

The above industries are giving employment by industries at world level. The consumer electronics industries are most expanded industry which providing 1.75 crore employment. Electronic industry is ranking first in the world at employment parameter. The real estate based industries are giving 1.71 crore employment whereas fast food and restaurants are giving 1.35 crore employments.

- **Industries and India**

(Source: - ASI (Annual Survey of Industries) Report 2019-20)

The above chart data is interpreting that the food products industry is employing 11.10%. The textile and apparel industry is employing 7.58% whereas Basic Metals 7.25%, Motor Vehicles 6.51%. The Chemical and Chemical Product industries are providing 5.61%, Rubber and Plastics 5.07%, Non Metallic

mineral industries 6.34% and other than these industries accounting 35.11%.

- **Sector Wise employment in India**

The majority population of Indian country is relying on the Agriculture sector for an employment following table is showing the sector wise employment of the country

Table 1.1 The availability of sector wise Employment

Sr. No.	Year	Agriculture	Industry	Service
1	2010-11	51.52	21.81	26.68
2	2011-12	49.26	23.49	27.53
3	2012-13	47	24.36	38.64
4	2013-14	46.50	24.37	29.13
5	2014-15	45.89	24.45	29.66
6	2015-16	45.26	24.54	30.20
7	2016-17	44.56	24.74	30.70
8	2017-18	43.93	24.86	31.21
9	2018-19	43.33	24.95	31.72
10	2019-20	42.60	25.12	32.28

(Source:- website: www.indiastats.com)

The above table 1.1 is showing sectorwise availability of employment. The primary sector (Agriculture & Allied) is providing highest share of percentage employment. The financial year 2010-11 is providing 51.52%, 2011-12 49.26% whereas 2012-13 has given 47%. The industrial sector is also giving

upward trend of employment percentage from 2010-11 21.81% to 25.12% in 2019-20. The service sector is has given 26.68% in 2010-11 to 32.28% in 2019-20. The dependency on agriculture has decreased of India from 51.52% to 42.60%.

• Conclusion

The Indian population is top ranked in the world. To employ this populated country is the biggest challenge to government agencies. India is developing nation and most of the population is involved in agriculture sector or primary sector it is accounted 51.52% in the year 2010-11 which had more than half share of total employment. The initial phase of independent India largely depended on agriculture but nowadays the industries and service sector has made important position to employment. The industrial sector is employing 25.12% in the year 2019-20 whereas service sector has employed 32.28% in same year. The flow of FDI (Foreign Direct Investments) is increasing in India for the year 2021-22 it was more than 6 lakh crore. The industrial sector and service sectors are expanding at good growth of the Indian country and it is giving the promising employment. To increase the employment, it is required to increase the investments in Micro, Small, Medium and Large scale industries.

• Bibliography

1. https://www.edu.gov.mb.ca/k12/cur/soctstud/frame_found_sr2/blms/4-1.pdf
2. Dr. Uma Pujar, MSMEs and Employment in India: an analytical study, IOSR Journal of Business and Management, Volume 16, Issue 5. Ver. II (May. 2014), PP 13-15
3. Abdulhossain Moghtadaee, Mansour Zarra Nezhad and Elaheh Ansari, (2006) The Role of Small Industries in Employment Generation and Economic Development in Maharashtra and Khuzestan, Quarterly Journal of Economic Review, 3(3), pp.01-22
4. Dr. Kalyan, N. B., Kumar Kalyan, & Padmavati, A., (2012) A Study on Employment Trends in India, Global Advanced Research Journal of Management & Business Studies, Vol.1 (6). Pp 173-180
5. Mrs. Manjula, (2022) Role of Industrial Sector in Employment Creation with Reference to Kolar District, International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts, Volume 10, Issue 11, Nov, PP. 01-12.
6. <https://facelesscompliance.com/40454/india-receives-highest-ever-fdi-of-over-rs-6-lakh-crores-in-2021-22>